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EDUCATORS

Each day, they teach with wisdom and care
Dearly guiding, with passion so rare
Unfolding dreams
Changing lives
Amidst struggles and plights.
Tireless efforts beyond tasks
Others' success, nothing more to ask
Raising lawyers and doctors among the many professions
Shaping the future of a nation